

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF SOLAR WOOD CUTTER

¹PROF ANDAGI. B.D,

²MAHESH.S.MALABADE,

³VIJAYARAJ.S.NIKAM, .

⁴MALLAPPA.S.KORI,

⁵VISHNU.B.DHONE

^{2,3,4, 5}:Students,Department of Mechanical Engineering, A.G.P.I.T. Solapur

¹Assistant Professor,Department of Mechanical Engineering,A.G.P.I.T. Solapur

ABSTRACT

Requirement of electricity of the world is increasing at very high rate because of industrial growth, increased and extensive use of electrical gadgets. Today world receives 80% of the energy from conventional non-renewable energy sources, So within short time span, all the sources will be completely exhausted. The best alternative source is solar energy. Solar energy can be used in many electrical appliances. This project deals with solar energy based wood cutting tool, Solar Based wood Cutter with Human Safety project is the project used to cutting woods with help of solar energy. This project uses the solar energy touting the woods without using electric energy or any fuel like diesel, petrol.

In this project we use the sensor for avoiding any accident for human safety. This system does not produce any hazardous gases or any substances to pollute environment. We implemented the speed variation for cutting various types of woods. It also run on electric supply but mainly runs solar power, In this project we try to reduce the cost of machine so it beneficial for people who are not affordable purchase the electric woodcutter or fuel based cutter.